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A **Sessão Internacional** é realizada pela **Superintendência de Relações Internacionais** com o objetivo de dar oportunidade aos estudantes de vivenciarem a experiência de apresentar trabalhos em inglês. A intenção é que os alunos se sintam motivados a participar de eventos internacionais. Ao apresentar a pesquisa em outras línguas nesse tipo de evento, há visibilidade nacional e internacional para o trabalho e para a instituição. A ação abre portas para colaborações científicas, por exemplo. A quinta edição da Sessão Internacional foi parte da programação do X Café Internacional da UEMA.

SUMÁRIO

(em ordem alfabética)

ALCHEMY OF POWER: PARADOXES OF AUTHORITARIANISM IN AMESTRIS AND BRAZIL

Autor(es): Julia Vitoria Martins Pessoa

Orientador: Prof. Dr. Ruan Bruzaca Didier

BLACK WOMEN SUBALTERNIZATION FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF PAULINE BREEDLOVE IN THE BLUEST EYE, BY TONI MORRISON

Autor(es): Carla Marina da Silva Torres de Sousa

Orientador: Prof. Dr. José Ailson Lemos de Souza

BRAZILIAN THINK TANKS AND THE ULTRALIBERALIST AGENDA: A CASE STUDY OF THE MEDIA COMPANY BRASIL PARALELO (2016-2020)

Autor(es): Alicia Souza de Oliveira, Nicole de Araújo Correa

Orientador: Prof. Dr. Thiago Allisson Cardoso de Jesus

BUMBA MEU BOI: WHEN CULTURE MEETS INTERNATIONAL DIPLOMACY AND IMPACTS THE LOCAL ECONOMY

Autor(es): Mirna Vitória de Santana Silva Campos, Samara de Menezes Anjos,

Orientador: Profa. Dra. Amanda Silva Madureira

CHINESE INFLUENCE OVER HOLLYWOOD: A SYMPTOM OF AMERICAN RELATIVE ECONOMIC DECLINE?

Autor(es): Arthur Franco Ribeiro, Geovanna Letícia Torres Mendonça

Orientador: Prof. Dr. Diogo de Almeida Viana dos Santos

CULTURE DIPLOMACY AND SOFT POWER: NEW STRATEGIES FOR PROJECTION IN THE INTERNATIONAL SYSTEM

Autor(es): Ana Tereza

Orientador: Profa. Dra. Amanda Silva Madureira

INDIA IN THE 21ST CENTURY: MULTILATERALISM AND STRATEGIC ALLIANCES AS A WAY TO RISE TO GLOBAL POWER

Autor(es): Thayze Raquel Ramos Lima

Orientador: Prof. Dr. Rodolfo Francisco Soares Nunes

INTERNATIONALIZATION AT UNIVERSIDADE ESTADUAL DO MARANHÃO: THE PRESENCE OF COLONIALITY IN ACADEMIC MOBILITY

Autor(es): Stefanie Zerba Monteiro

Orientador: Prof. Dr. Bráulio Roberto de Castro Loureiro

KOWLOON WALLED CITY: A PARALLEL WITH THE PAST AND THE CURRENT URBAN PLANNING

Autor(es): Lauanne Leonardo Santos, Geovana Carneiro Santos

Orientador: Prof. Dr. Amanda Silva Madureira

OBSTACLES OF THE CONSOLIDATION OF EXTENSION IN TECHNICAL CONSULTANCY ON ARCHITECTURE AND URBANISM COURSES IN BRAZIL

Autor(es): Arthur Vinicius Pinheiro da Silva, Kayo de Oliveira Reis Brito

Orientador: Prof. Dr. Amanda Silva Madureira

RUSSIAN STRATEGIC CULTURE: RUSSIA-UKRAINE WAR AND THE ROLE OF CULTURE

Autor(es): Karina de Araujo Oliveira da Silva

Orientador: Prof. Dr. Thiago Allisson Cardoso de Jesus

SOFT POWER - CULTURAL INFLUENCE IN INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

Autor(es): Luiza Pereira de Sousa

Orientador: Prof. Diogo de Almeida Viana dos Santos

THE AFRICAN INFLUENCE ON CULTURAL MANIFESTATIONS IN THE STATE OF MARANHÃO, BRAZIL

Autor(es): Ana Luísa Pires Costa, Helena Cristina Nogueira de Alencar

Orientador: Prof. Dr. Amanda Silva Madureira

THE EFFECTS OF WORLD WAR II ON FASHION: Transformations, Restrictions, and New Trends

Autor(es): Livya Ellen Ivo Araújo, Louise Carolina Nascimento Matos

Orientador: Prof. Dr. Diogo de Almeida Viana dos Santos

THE HISTORY OF BRAZIL'S INTELLIGENCE AGENCIES: ITS IMPORTANCE AND ITS SITUATION IN THE WORLD CONTEXT

Autor(es): Monique Mendes Costa

Orientador: Prof. Dr. Amanda Silva Madureira

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE PAJUBÁ DIALECT IN THE CONSTRUCTION OF AN LGBTQIAPN+ IDENTITY IN CONTEMPORARY BRAZIL

Autor(es): Manoel da Anunciação Silva Neto, Maria Eduarda Ferreira

Orientador: Prof. Dr. Amanda Silva Madureira

THE LIMITS OF THE INTERNATIONAL INTERVENTION IN RELIGION

Autor(es): Ana Beatriz Santos Furtado, Beatriz Silva Alves de Oliveira, Laryssa Fernanda Castro Silva

Orientador: Prof. Dr. Amanda Silva Madureira

THE PHENOMENON OF UBERIZATION AND NEW FORMS OF PRECARIZATION OF WORK RELATIONSHIPS

Autor(es): Ana Thais Teixeira Pereira

Orientador: Profa. Dra. Zulene Muniz Barbosa

THE RISE OF FAR-RIGHT MOVEMENTS IN EUROPE AND THEIR IMPACT ON MULTILATERALISM: ERODING COOPERATION IN THE 21ST CENTURY

Autor(es): Rafael Magalhães de Lima Silva, Larissa Dourado Ribeiro

Orientador: Prof. Dr. Amanda Silva Madureira

THE THIRD SECTOR AND ITS COOPERATION FOR DEVELOPMENT AND ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION, THROUGH THE USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

Autor(es): Adriely Gonçalves Cunha

Orientador: Prof. Me. Rodolfo F.S. Nunes

WHERE ARE THE WOMEN? UNPACKING THE BARRIERS TO FEMALE REPRESENTATION IN INTERNATIONAL POLITICS

Autor(es): Any Jamily Aires Pereira

Orientador: Prof. Dr. Thiago Allisson Cardoso de Jesus

SOFT POWER - CULTURAL INFLUENCE IN INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

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INTRODUCTION

This extended abstract aims to explore how soft power, and the culture industry are intertwined, demonstrating how countries and global actors use these mechanisms to exert influence and win adherence to their values, policies and ways of life. The analysis of these two tools together offers a critical view of how power on the international stage has been transformed, showing that, in the contemporary world, power is not only exercised through force, but also through the ability to attract and win over minds.

In this way, the concept of soft power is discussed from the point of view of theorist and writer Joseph Nye, highlighting how a country's culture, political values and ideologies play a central role in building this type of power. In this way, this concept joins that of the culture industry - which treats culture as a commodity, with the aim of generating profit and, at the same time, exercising social control - developed by the philosophers of the Frankfurt School, Theodor Adorno and Max Horkheimer.

Thus, this paper aims to deepen the understanding of the intersection between soft power and the culture industry, analyzing how these two forces collaborate to shape contemporary international power.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology adopted in this work will be based on qualitative and exploratory research, using a combination of bibliographic and documentary sources, with the aim of analyzing the concept of soft power and its relationship with the cultural industry in the context of international relations. The research will be structured around the analysis of academic books, scientific articles and reliable sources from specialized websites, which will allow for an in-depth understanding of the themes and their interconnections.

SOFT POWER

Joseph Nye, theorist of the concept of “soft power” and author of *Soft Power: The Means to Success in World Politics* (2004), points out that culture is one of the main sources of soft power, as it influences the perception of a country's values. The concept emerged in the 1980s, but its practice had been observed for a long time. A historical example can be seen in the rise of the Catholic Church in the Roman Empire, which expanded its power without the use of weapons, only through faith. However, this strategy could not sustain itself and involved alliances that often went against religious principles, generating popular discontent. Thus, hard power - which in this case refers to the use of force, i.e. violence and weapons to exert domination over different peoples - proved to be ineffective in the long term, since it was done against the will of a people; soft power - conquering through ideologies, such as faith - proved to be more effective. However, as soon as these ideologies began to mix with hard power - such as the alliances made by the church with political leaders - there was resistance from the masses.

Thus, according to Joseph Nye, soft power:

It's the ability to get what you want through attention, not coercion or erasure. It arises from the attractiveness of a country through its culture, its politics and its ideals. When you get others to admire your ideals and want what you want, you don't have to spend a lot on political incentives and sanctions to move them in your direction. (JOSEPH, 2005, p.31)

In this logic, over the years the use of hard power has become something condemned by the international community, since with the advancement of debates on human rights, using war as a form of conquest brings the implication of not obeying these rights, corroborating that a nation begins to be isolated from the international community, that is, waging a direct war today requires the abdication of several international connections, as is the case in the Ukrainian War, in which Russia is undergoing several sanctions, such as its withdrawal from the European Union. Swift¹.

¹ The main function of this system is to enable the exchange of banking information and international financial transfers.

V SESSÃO INTERNACIONAL – 28 DE NOVEMBRO DE 2024

In this way, the Cold War period was one of the times when soft power was used the most, since there was no direct battle between the US and the Soviet Union, but various means were used to convey the idea, both internally and in their foreign policies, that the ideology of each of the two countries was “the right one”. Thus, the cultural media became a strong ally for each nation, in that through advertisements, songs, films like Captain America, which brought the idea of an American hero fighting a secret agency that wanted to dominate the world, were artifacts to sell an idea on both the domestic and international scene about the promotion of an ideology, that is, using only economic and political factors was not and is no longer enough to promote hegemony.

CULTURE INDUSTRY

The concept of the culture industry debated by Frankfurt School philosophers Theodor Adorno and Max Horkheimer argues that in capitalist society, cultural production, once an art form, is now treated as a commodity. Instead of being created for reflection or creative expression, culture is now mass-produced with the aim of generating profit. Much of this has happened due to the countless technological advances that today enable people to have access to diverse cultures and thus be targeted to become buyers of various cultural elements.

An example of this transformation of art into a product can be seen in the advancement of the Hollywood industry, in which the idea of a perfect American life, the so-called American Way of Life, is transmitted through the screen in many films, so that different cultures are influenced by a culture other than their own, Because viewers look to these elements as a way of escaping their routine, they find themselves influenced in the way they dress, in what they listen to, in their consumption patterns, which favors the internationalization of various brands such as Coca-Cola, Nike and Disney, and in this way the individual is influenced by various cultural values that are different from their own.

Thus, from the moment the state starts to use the mechanisms of the Cultural Industry, it turns its ideals from just a means of leisure into a policy capable of influencing different societies in their consumption patterns, but also in the way they act socially, and what is seen as outside the bubble of this industry is analyzed as socially “weird”. Therefore, Adorno and Horkheimer (1985) say that culture not only helps to curb barbaric instincts, but also helps to prevent revolutionary instincts from being aroused.

V SESSÃO INTERNACIONAL – 28 DE NOVEMBRO DE 2024

Therefore, the tool of soft power has become a great ally, so that countries today can use coercive tools, such as the culture industry, to propagate their ideologies in their international and domestic policies, winning over followers to their way of life and consumption.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The research reveals how soft power and the culture industry are intertwined as tools of influence in international relations. Soft power, according to Joseph Nye, is a strategy of attraction and persuasion, exemplified by the use of the United States during the Cold War, which spread its ideals through films and music. The research also explored Adorno and Horkheimer's concept of the culture industry, highlighting the transformation of culture into merchandise and its role in social control, shaping behavior and values through the media.

Therefore, the research suggests that power on the contemporary international stage is built not only through military or economic strength, but also through the ability to attract other countries through cultural and ideological values.

CONCLUSION

The research has shown that soft power and the cultural industry are interconnected and essential strategies for building power on the contemporary international stage. By highlighting how soft power works through cultural and ideological attraction, it became evident that nations, such as the United States, use culture as an instrument to promote their values and expand their global influence; and by analyzing the concept of the culture industry, it was possible to see how culture becomes a commodity, not only generating profit, but also shaping social behaviors and attitudes. Therefore, the study highlighted the importance of understanding these forms of power, which, unlike military force, operate through more subtle but equally effective means in promoting ideologies and building hegemonies.

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